

Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data

The consortium of **DATAMITE** — “**Data Monetization, Interoperability, Trading & Exchange**” — is proud to announce the official start of this European initiative, funded by the **European Commission** under the **Horizon Europe** research and innovation programme.

DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework to improve Data Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the monetisation potential at two levels:

- **At internal level**, users will have tools to improve the quality and management of their data, the adherence to **FAIR** principles. They will be able to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustable and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.
- **At external level**, users will boost their data sharing capabilities while keeping the control of their data, providing new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders.

DATAMITE delivers a modular, open-source and multi-domain Framework, in the form of software modules, training and business materials.

The architecture envisioned for **DATAMITE** enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential instructor on their onboarding of SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, **DATAMITE’s solutions will function as catalysts to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.**

DATAMITE will validate the results in **3 different use cases** with a total of **6 pilots**, demonstrating that the Framework is interoperable and usable in different domains and user needs, as:

- 1) Intra-corporate, multi-domain data exchange.
- 2) Data trading/sharing in Data Spaces.

- 3) Integration with other initiatives as Data Markets, EU AI-on-demand platform, or DIHs.

Sectors covered by the pilots are **agriculture, energy, industrial and manufacturing, and climate.**

DATAMITE is a 3-year-project, led by [Instituto Tecnológico de Informatica \(ITI\)](https://www.iti.es), and composed of **26 partners from 12 countries**, which will bring together key actors of the data value chain, key experts in Legal and SSH aspects to guarantee legal and societal compliance and facilitators on open-source community building and standardisation.

Know more about DATAMITE project here: www.datamite-horizon.eu

Contact us!

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